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Digital Detoxification and Academic Performance of Business Education Undergraduate Students in Rivers State Universities

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the study was to investigate digital detoxification and academic performance among Business Education undergraduate students in Rivers State Universities. The study adopted correlation study design. Two specific objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consist of 1,820 undergraduate Business Education students from Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE). The stratified random sampling techniques was adopted draw a sample size of 790 students for the study. The instruments for data collection was a self-made instrument title” Digital Detoxification Questionnaire (DDQ) and Academic Performance Rating Scale Questionnaire (APRSQ). The instruments was validated by three experts, one in measurement and Evaluation, and two from Business Education department of River State University. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded 0.84 and 0.81 respectively out of 790 copies of instruments distributed, one hundred percent return was recorded and collected were analysed using PPMC to answer research questions and t-transformations to test the null hypotheses. The study found positive linear relationship between digital fast and Business Education students academic performance amongst others. Based on the findings, it was recommended amongst other that students should continue the use of digital fast in detoxifying their devices to increase their academic performance.

Key Words: Academic Performance, Business Education, Digital Detoxification, Business Education Undergraduate Students.

INTRODUCTION

University education according to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014), is referred to as the education a person gets after a successful completion of secondary education. It is the final level of education in the current 9-3-4 structure of education in Nigeria (Yahaya, 2020). The 9-3-4 system of education consists of a 9years Universal Basic Education (UBE), 3years period of secondary education and at least 4years of higher education. University education provides skilled manpower directly to the labour market and the economy and it is therefore, expected that its products should possess sound knowledge and adequate skill necessary to meet the challenges and expectations of the world of work and solve situational problems and achieve expected results (Panadero, 2020). University education is the bedrock to the socio-economic and political development of any nation. Universities as a stronghold of learning, supplies the skilled manpower for economic growth and development of any society. Society depends on university education for tackling emerging societal problems and meeting new developmental

aspirations (Owen, 2020), the main activities carried out in the universities, which are teaching, commercialization of research findings, research, community development, transfer of worthwhile knowledge and value and generation of highly skilled personnel to serve the industries and society towards a better future, which Business Education programme is also included towards finding a solution to the problems of the society.

Business Education involves the acquisition and development of skills and competencies, knowledge, attitudes and attributes which are needed for effective managing an enterprise and for lucrative service. It is the intellectual and vocational preparation of people for earning a living in the contemporary industrial and business environment. It is the sum total of knowledge, skills and attitude that are required for successful promoting and administering business enterprises and education for and about business (Akpomi, 2019). Business Education is concerned with the education of the individual for business and about business; The former focussed on those who need career in business and the later for all students in the entire school system irrespective of their career aspirations. Accordingly, Akpomi (2019), Business Education encompasses knowledge, attitude and skills needed by all citizens in order to effectively manage personal business and economic system and make advancement in a broad range of business careers. Business Education is one of the noble professions that create wealth and development in society, provides jobs, fosters innovations and improves livings (Amadi, 2022). The primary goal of Business Education is to equip Business Education students with the knowledge, skills and competencies needed to succeed in the business as well as in life.

Business Education students are individuals who are pursuing academic programme in business Education, such as Bachelor's or Master's degrees in Business Education (Bsc or Msc/M.Ed). These students are typically motivated, ambitious and eager to learn the skills and knowledge required to succeed in the business world. According to Ogwunte and Olali (2024), Business Education plays a crucial role in shaping her students into competent, confident and effective business professionals. Through Business Education, students acquire a solid understanding of business fundamentals, including, accounting, management, marketing and operation knowledge. Through Business Education, students also develop practical skills such as data analysis, financial, modelling, and developmental, skills. Business Education students learn essential soft skills including communication, teamwork, leadership and time management skills. Business Education students connect with professionals, entrepreneurs and academics in the field, expanding their networks horizons through the business processes. Business processes and system, production and scientific research, supply chains and other activities that drive our daily lives (healthcare, food production, commercial activities etc) are gradually more dependent on digital technologies (Bupo & Akpomi, 2023).

Digital technology has made the transfer of information from teachers to students very easy and attractive. Students now have devices such as laptops, tablets, smartphones and others, that have access to the internet from which they communicate rapidly with their friends and peers (Kour, 2021). With the rapid advancement in technology, learning content can be easily shared through various platforms and systems. In a bid to ensure that university Business Education students are equipped with appropriate knowledge and skills that are essential to meet with the economic and global expectations, it is necessary that university Business Education students be given every available opportunity to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for results yielding competition globally.

However, leaders, educators and researchers in the education sectors have raised alarm over the misuse of mobile devices by students, especially university undergraduate students. This may be explained in the Fact that students tend to spend more time fiddling with the phone in the classroom during and after lecture period, in examination hall, even when walking on the road, when on the bed, when eating, when cooking and so one which has adversely affected their academic performance.

Digital Detoxification refers to a period of time when a person refrains from using technological devices. it is a process of temporarily taking time off one's mobile devices such as smartphones, tablets, computers, televisions and social sites. Digital detoxification which can also be called digital detox or detoxing is often seen as a way to focus on real-life situations without distractions. By temporarily

foregoing digital devices, people can let go of stress that stems from constant connectivity and avoid getting addicted to their mobile devices. By welcoming and engaging in digital detoxification, Business Education students can stay focused on their academic activities without getting distracted by their technological devices, especially their smart phones. Technology addiction is not formally recognized as a disorder, many experts believe that tech and devices overuse represent a very real behavioural addiction that can lead to physical, psychological, social and academic problems (Selwyn, 2023).

Fortunately, smart phones have made life much easier in so many ways, yet the technology on these devices have been dominating lives. According to scout as cited in Winnick (2021), most people tap their smart phones on the average of 2,617 times per day. This is a serious distraction especially for Business Education students who are going through training and development process, which have shown that powerful computers made in the form of mobile devices most people hold and keep in their pockets can be distracting for even the most disciplined adult. Research in the educational sphere demonstrates that using mobile devices and social media while learning new material reduces comprehension and impairs academic performance (Kumar et al, 2024). Studies have also shown that even if cell phones are turned off, turned face down or put away, their mere presence reduces people's cognitive capacity (Nield, (2022). There are several ways in which students are required to engage in digital detoxifications, these includes; the introduction of the use of digital-fast, do-not-disturb, app-attack, tech-free zone, dumb-phone and internet-access-blocking for Business Education undergraduate student's academic performance improvement.

The introduction of the digital-fast which is mapping out some time, especially during lecture periods to keep completely away from mobile devices to enable Business Education students give full attention and concentration to their academic achievement. The idea of digital-fast is to temporarily unplug your device or switching off your device that is 'abstention', and this can be done for few hours, for example (8am-2pm), after which the phone can be switched back on. This will allow for complete concentration during lecture and academic work periods. The use of this strategy, will guarantee maximum concentration towards the task ahead thereby yielding adequate expected outcome.

The activation of the 'do-not-disturb app on the mobile phone device is a good way of engaging in a digital detox for a period of time to allow for complete concentration on tasks at hand and ahead and thereby give full concentration and participation in the teaching and learning processes. The constant stream of emails, text messages, Facebook, WhatsApp, and other non-stop push notifications can be quite distracting especially in the midst of teaching and learning activities (Kumar, et al ,2024). The activation of do-not-disturb mode is one easy way to put these notifications on hold, for a period of time, to allow students give maximum concentration on the academic activity at hand. The introduction of the app-attack which requires that Business Education students engaged in the process of deleting unnecessary apps that pop up unsolicited notifications that will obviously cause distractions on the classroom is one of the ways Business Education students are required to engage in digital detoxification for improvement of academic performance. Numerous apps offer exciting and educative features ranging from games, education, business, banking, and entertainment to social networking. They are precision engineered to create and feed our interaction neediness.

The application of the above suggested ways by Business Education university students, educators and university authorities, will ultimately yield a favourable result and subsequently ensure the meeting up of expected objective in students' academic performance in universities in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The wide spread use of digital devices and social media has become an integral part of modern life, particularly among undergraduate students. While digital technology as opened up new avenues for learning and communication, it has also introduced a range of distractions that can negatively impact academic performance. Business Education undergraduate students in River State universities are no exception to this trend, and there is growing concern about the impact of digital addiction on their academic success.

The importance of digital detoxification cannot be overstated. Digital detoxification refers to the practice of abstaining from digital devices or limiting their uses to specific times of the day. This can help students develop self-control and discipline in their digital device use, improve their focus and productivity, and promote deeper learning and retention of academic materials. By taking regular breaks from digital devices, students can recharge, reflect and refocus on their academic goals. Despite the important of digital detoxification, many Business Education undergraduate students in Rivers State universities struggle with digital addiction. These students often find themselves constantly checking their phones, social media and emails, and feel worried when they are unable to navigate. This can lead to a vicious cycle of distraction, decreased productivity, and poor time management. The constant stream of notifications can be overwhelming, causing students to feel stressed and worried. Many Business Education undergraduate students are unable to disconnect from their digital devices, leading to decrease focus, productivity and academic performance. This can have serious consequences, including poor grades, decreased motivation and a lack of interest in academic pursuits. Furthermore, the impact of digital addiction can extend beyond academic performance, affecting students mental and physical health, relationship and overall well-being.

This situation confronting undergraduate Business Education students in Rivers State universities makes one wonder whether digital detoxification dimensions enhance academic performance among undergraduate Business Education students in Rivers State. If yes, then the question is put; is there link between digital detoxification and academic performance of Business Education undergraduate students? The call for the need to investigate the link between Digital Detoxification and Academic Performance among Business Education undergraduate students in Rivers State universities.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between Digital Detoxification and Academic Performance of Business Education undergraduate students in Rivers State University (RSU), and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between digital-fast and Business Education undergraduate student's academic performance in Rivers State University (RSU), and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) in Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the relationship between do-not-disturb and Business Education undergraduate student's academic performance in Rivers State University (RSU), and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between digital-fast and Business Education undergraduate student's academic performance in Rivers State Universities?
2. What is the relationship between do-not-disturb and Business Education undergraduate student's academic performance in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between digital-fast and Business Education undergraduate students' academic performance in Rivers State Universities.
2. There is no significant relationship between do-not-disturb and Business Education

METHOD

The study adopted correlation study design, with a population of 1,820 undergraduate Business Education Students from Rivers State University (RSU = 375) and Ignatius Ajuru, University of Education (1,145) students respectively. This information is shown on Table 3.1 below

Table 1: Population Distribution

S/n	Institutions	Business Education Students				Academic session	Total
		Level 100	Level 200	Level 300	Level 400		
1.	R/S University	146	79	114	36	2024/2025	375
3.	Ignatius Ajuru Uni. Edu.	488	444	513	-	2024/2025	1,445
Total		634	523	627	36		1,820

Source: Department of Business Education Exams and Records Office 2025 session.

The sample size of the study was 790 respondents. Two (2) instruments used for data collection in this study are self-structured instruments titled ‘Questionnaire on Digital Detoxification Questionnaire (DDQ) and Academic Performance Rating scale (APRSQ). The questionnaire is made up of two sections, section A and B. section A consist of items seeking the personal information of the respondents such as institution and gender while Section B deals with the respondents from questionnaire items. The responses on the questionnaire structure on a 4point rating scale of; Strongly Agree (SA-4points), Agree (A-3points), Disagree (D-2points) and Strongly Disagree (SD-1point). The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by two experts from the Department of Business Education and one Measurement and Evaluation expert all of Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Each of the experts was given a copy of the instrument to eliminate any irrelevant statement presented by the researcher and made suggestions for the improvement of the research work. Their suggestions were integrated into the final copy of the questionnaire used for data collection for the study. To establish the reliability of the instrument, copies of the questionnaire was administered to twenty-five (25) level 200, 300 and 400 Business Education students in University of Uyo, which is not part of the population of the study. The two sets of questionnaires were re-administered to the same group three days afterwards. Cronbach Alpha Statistic was used to correlate the two sets of data and the reliability coefficient (r) which yielded 0.847 and 0.815, respectively.

The researcher engaged the services of three (3) assistants who helped to administer the instrument to the respondents. The assistants were enlightened on how to administer the seven hundred and ninty copies of the instrument on the respondents of the study. However, 790 copies were completely filled and returned, which accounted for 67% returned on questionnaire distributed. Data collected were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the six (6) research questions and also were used in testing the six (6) hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance with the aid of statistical packages in social science (SPSS). A benchmark/Decision rule as proposed by Ahiazu (2023) was adopted as indicated below to guide the interpretation of the results between the variables. The decision rule was that, the null hypotheses was rejected when the critical r value is greater than the calculated r value and was accepted when the critical r value is less than the calculated r value. Ahiazu (2023) gave the following parameters as benchmark for interpreting correlation coefficient (r):

1. 0.8 – 1.0 = very strong relationship
2. 0.6 – 0.79 = strong relationship
3. 0.4 – 0.59 = moderate relationship
4. 0.2 – 0.39 = weak relationship
5. 0.0 – 0.19 = very weak or no relationship

ANALYSIS OF DATA AND RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between digital-fast and Business Education undergraduate student's academic performance in Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) in Rivers State?*

Table 4.1: Respondents Rating of Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient on the relationship between digital fast and Business Education Undergraduates students' academic performance (N = 790)

Variables	ΣX	ΣY	X^2	Y^2	N	ΣXY	R	Rmks
Digital Fast (X)	629.46		2064.01		790			
Business Education undergraduate Academic Performance (Y)		682.28		2420.61		2195.00	0.09	VSR

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

The analysis in Table 4.1 presents Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the relationship between Digital Fast and Business Education undergraduate students' academic performance in Rivers State universities. The analysis showed that r-value was 0.09 which connotes a very strong relationship between the above mentioned variables. The correlation coefficient of 0.09 indicates a positive linear relationship between Digital Fast and Business Education students' academic performance.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between do-not-disturb and Business Education undergraduate student's academic performance in RSU and IAUE in Rivers State?*

Table 4.2: Respondents Rating of Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient on the relationship between Do-not-Disturb and Business Education Undergraduates students' academic performance. (N = 790)

Variables	ΣX	ΣY	X^2	Y^2	N	ΣXY	r	Remarks
Do-not-Disturb (X)	605.34		1891.84		790			
Business Education undergraduate Academic Performance (Y)		682.28		2420.61		2109.27	0.06	Strong Relationship

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

The analysis in Table 4.2 showed that (r = 0.06) indicating that a strong relation between Do not-Disturb and Business Education undergraduates in Rivers State. This implies that an increase in Do-not-Disturb tends to increase Business Education undergraduate academic performance. However, the relationship is not strong.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Relationship between Digital Fast and Business Education undergraduate students academic performance in universities in Rivers State.

Finding from research question one on how Digital Fast relates to Digital detoxification and Academic performance of Business Education undergraduate students in universities in Rivers State showed a negligible positive relationship. The hypothesis in this regard was retained as the calculated t-value was less than t-critical value. This findings is in agreement with scholars and researchers like Hossain (2019)

and Khan (2022); who are of the opinion that digital fast for academic performance has obvious advantages; enhances focus for the present, enhances attentive learning, enhances interpersonal relationship, increases high quality sleep, reduces class distractions, easy storage of information in the brain, more attention to real life issues, improves academic performance and enhances better ideas for creativity. This is to say that when students engage in digital detoxification using digital fast approach, it reduces the constant use of smartphones and enables one have a sound health. Lahue et al (2024) who posited that digital detox using digital fast gives the mind and body an opportunity to restore their natural rhythms and enhance relationship and productivity.

Relationship between Do-not Disturb and Academic Performance of undergraduate Business Education students.

Findings from research question two with regard to Do-not-Disturb mode and Academic Performance of undergraduate students of Business Education in universities revealed a negligible positive relationship. The implication is that do-not-disturb utilization aided by the use of smartphones and other digital devices, are boosting students' ways of living in every area of life but can really be a distraction when users' needs to focus or be productive with the aim of achieving desired goals. This view is in support of Hossain (2019) as foundational that smartphones and digital devices can pop up thousands of notifications capable of reducing the attention of users, more especially, students in the classroom that are expected to give full attention to the lecture being thought or attention to the project they are expected to complete within a speculated time frame. The corresponding hypothesis formulated was retained. The findings support the view of Danilo, Nami and Kyung (2019) as foundational who is of the opinion that, maximum concentration during lectures in the university and at workplace improves academic outcomes, and self-control outcome in academic context, reduced distraction when one activates the DND mode to shut all or part of the notifications, messages and alerts that would normally pop up into the device. The researcher is of the opinion that Business Education undergraduate students should practice Do-Not-Disturb mode towards academic performance to combat screen addiction, and attract maximum attention to immediate surroundings, and encourage high project work and healthy living.

CONCLUSION

The relationship between the variables considered was highlighted in the study. It indicated very strong relationship as well low strong relationship between the variables considered. It becomes necessary for Business Education student to practice digital detoxification to enable them pay better attention to their academic work and eliminate constant check up on social media.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1 Students should continue the use of digital fast in detoxifying their devices to increase their academic performance.
- 2 Students should set their smartphone on do-not-disturb mode so as to eliminate all notification that pops up unnecessary to enable them pay attention on the task at hand.

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